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**THE IMPORTANCE OF HELICOBACTER PYLORI IN THE
ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF GASTRODUODENAL DISEASES**

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Annotation. *The event taking place in stomach mucous in participation of different phenotypical Helicobacter pylori strains and changes of system and local immunity, promote development of intestinal metaplasia and atrophy. These process in some case lead to gastritis development and in another cases to ulcer and cancer genesis.*

Key words. *Gastroduodenal diseases, Helicobacter pylori, virulence, strains, metaplasia, carcinogenesis.*

Chronic gastritis (CG) and peptic ulcer disease (PUD) have long been the subject of extensive scientific investigation. Significant progress in understanding the etiology and pathogenesis of these diseases, as well as improvements in diagnostic and therapeutic approaches, was achieved after the discovery of a microorganism in 1982 by R. Warren and B. Marshall [1]. Initially designated Campylobacter pylori, the microorganism was reclassified in 1989 as Helicobacter pylori (H. pylori) following serological identification and clarification of its structural characteristics. This discovery represented a major milestone in modern clinical gastroenterology.

The role of Helicobacter pylori in the pathogenesis of chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, gastric adenocarcinoma, and gastric MALT lymphoma has been convincingly demonstrated. However, in most cases H. pylori infection results in chronic gastritis, while peptic ulcer disease and gastric cancer develop in less than 1% of infected individuals. This variability is associated with differences in bacterial strains, their virulence properties, host immune status, and environmental factors.

Several virulence factors of Helicobacter pylori have been extensively studied, including flagella-mediated motility, enzymatic activity (urease and superoxide dismutase), and bacterial adhesion to gastric epithelial cells. Bacterial motility is considered one of the key determinants of virulence and correlates with the severity of inflammatory changes in the gastric mucosa. Despite the established role of adhesion and cytotoxicity, high urease activity remains an important virulence determinant [2].

Recent studies have focused on phenotypic markers of Helicobacter pylori virulence. Despite significant genomic heterogeneity, H. pylori strains are commonly classified into two phenotypic types. Type I strains express the vacuolating cytotoxin (VacA) and cytotoxin-associated antigen (CagA), whereas Type II strains lack these virulence-associated structures. Type I strains are

associated with peptic ulcer disease and gastric carcinoma, while Type II strains predominantly induce chronic gastritis.

CagA⁺/VacA⁺ *Helicobacter pylori* strains exhibit pronounced cytotoxic effects and stimulate interleukin-8 (IL-8) secretion, resulting in marked mononuclear and polymorphonuclear infiltration of the gastric mucosa. These strains induce intense inflammatory responses, particularly in the antral region of the stomach. Their presence is associated with mucosal erosions, degeneration of surface epithelial cells, decreased mucus secretion, and the development of peptic ulcers. In addition, active gastritis and intestinal metaplasia are frequently observed, potentially contributing to carcinogenesis [3].

Inflammatory processes induced by *Helicobacter pylori* involve epithelial cells, macrophages, monocytes, polymorphonuclear leukocytes, and T- and B-lymphocytes as both effector and target cells [4]. Currently, three principal mechanisms underlying *H. pylori*-induced gastric mucosal damage have been identified. The first mechanism is characterized by an early innate immune response manifested by pronounced polymorphonuclear infiltration of the gastric mucosa, mediated by bacterial factors and IL-8 production by epithelial cells.

The second mechanism involves direct epithelial damage caused by *Helicobacter pylori* and the expression of chemotactic factors [5]. Bacterial phospholipases disrupt cellular membranes, increase membrane permeability, impair mucosal regeneration, and enhance leukotriene synthesis, thereby amplifying inflammatory responses.

The third mechanism is associated with the adaptive immune response to *Helicobacter pylori* infection, involving both T- and B-cell-mediated immunity. The inflammatory process is regulated by cytokines, including interleukins, leukotrienes, interferons, and tumor necrosis factors. During infection, immune-mediated damage becomes the predominant cause of gastric mucosal injury [6].

The gastric lamina propria is infiltrated by cytotoxic CD8⁺ lymphocytes, intraepithelial lymphocytes, natural killer (NK) cells, and CD4⁺ T-helper cells. Among these, CD4⁺ T-lymphocytes play a central role. These cells express IL-2 receptors, while gastric epithelial cells express HLA-DR class molecules induced by *Helicobacter pylori* antigens. Activation of mononuclear cells by IL-8 promotes leukocyte migration into the gastric mucosa.

T-lymphocytes produce cytokines such as IL-6 and IL-10, which stimulate secondary autoimmune responses through B-cell activation. During *Helicobacter pylori* infection, short-lived IgM antibodies and specific IgA seroconversion occur locally, while the presence of IgG antibodies in peripheral blood reflects the development of a systemic immune response [7,8]. Thus, *Helicobacter pylori* induces both innate and antigen-specific immune responses.

In peptic ulcer disease, immune disturbances are particularly pronounced and are characterized by a reduction in activated T-lymphocytes, polymorphonuclear leukocytosis, and decreased phagocytic activity. Several studies report a decrease in CD4⁺ T-helper cells during ulcer recurrence, whereas others describe reductions in CD8⁺ and CD16⁺ T-lymphocytes along with increased immune surveillance indices.

Contamination of the gastric mucosa with *Helicobacter pylori* leads to reduced immune reactivity, which is considered a secondary pathogenetic mechanism contributing to ulcer development. During disease progression, a decrease in all T-lymphocyte subpopulations and a reduction in B-lymphocyte levels are observed, although some studies report variable B-cell responses [9].

Data on humoral immunity remain inconsistent. Some authors report increased levels of IgG during the acute phase of peptic ulcer disease, whereas others identify elevated local IgA levels in *H. pylori*-associated chronic gastritis and peptic ulcer disease as a specific marker of immune response.

In patients with chronic gastritis and peptic ulcer disease, reduced activity of natural killer cells and decreased leukocyte blast transformation responses have been observed compared with individuals with duodenal ulcer disease, although functional activity is increased in gastric ulcer patients [10].

Different phenotypic and genotypic strains of *Helicobacter pylori* have different degrees of virulence, which in some cases leads to gastritis, in some cases to ulceration and carcinogenesis. The result of chronic gastritis is morphological changes - intestinal metaplasia, atrophy and the formation of malignant tumors in the stomach.

Thus, either helicobacteriosis or dysbacteriosis is determined in patients with chronic gastritis and peptic ulcer disease [11]. Analogous or similar results were obtained recently both in our country and abroad. It was established that streptococci, prevatella, and fusobacteria are the main microflora colonizing the stomach in its diseases [12]. These data were obtained during the study of the bacterial composition of the stomach by methods of deep sequencing of amplified 16SpRNA (cloning). In total, 127 phylotypes and 5 dominant genera (*Streptococcus*, *Prevatella*, *Fusobacterium*, *Rothia*, *Veilonella*) were identified.

Infection with *H. pylori* leads to the development of chronic active gastritis of varying severity in all infected persons. Against the background of gastritis, the risk of developing other *H. pylori*-associated diseases, including peptic ulcer disease and malignant lesions of the stomach, increases. The variability of the pattern of development of *H. pylori*-associated disease against the background of chronic gastritis is caused by various virulence and pathogenic properties of the bacterial strain, genetic features of the macroorganism, and environmental factors. In general, for *H. pylori*-positive patients, the risk of IBD during life is 10-20%, stomach cancer - 1-2%, and MALT-lymphoma of the stomach - 0.01-0.1% [13].

According to the last systematic review of 2017, about 4.35 billion people are infected with this microorganism, which corresponds to 45.4% of the Earth's population. At the same time, the highest prevalence rates of *H. pylori* 7 infection are observed in developing countries, reaching 70-90% of the population. The highest rate of *H. pylori* infection is observed in Africa (70.1%), while the lowest infection rate of the population (24.4%) is found in the countries of Oceania. Among individual countries, the lowest level of infection prevalence was noted in Switzerland (18.9%), and the highest - in Nigeria (87.7%).

Numerous studies have shown that infection with *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) is the absolutely dominant etiological factor of chronic gastritis worldwide. Taking into account this fact, the expert council reached the final consensus of Maastricht VI 2022. It is recommended to consider *H. pylori* as a pathogen, infection with which always leads to the development of chronic gastritis [14]. The prevalence of chronic gastritis associated with *H. pylori* infection is about 44.3–48.5%, and 80–90% of cases of the disease are asymptomatic. In *H. pylori*-infected patients with dyspepsia, in whom another pathology of the gastroduodenal zone was ruled out endoscopically, clinical manifestations can be treated within the framework of *H. pylori*-associated chronic gastritis, if after successful eradication therapy it was possible to achieve a stable remission of symptoms. However, patients with persistent dyspeptic symptoms, despite successful eradication therapy, may be considered patients with functional dyspepsia. Modern endoscopic methods (narrow-spectral endoscopy (NBI), high-resolution endoscopy, chromoendoscopy, laser confocal endomicroscopy) are accurate and reproducible methods for diagnosing precancerous changes in the mucous membrane [15]. At the same time, the diagnosis of chronic gastritis requires mandatory histological detection of inflammatory cells in the lamina propria of the mucous membrane of the stomach. The goals of chronic gastritis therapy are permanent suppression of dyspeptic manifestations of the disease (if present), as well as resolution of inflammatory processes and prevention of progression of precancerous changes in the gastric mucosa. Mainly, achievement of these goals is determined by timely diagnosis of *H. pylori* infection and successful eradication therapy.

In connection with the above, scientists report that a promising direction of modern research is the study of ways to control *H. pylori* infection, preventing the occurrence of a pronounced local inflammatory reaction in the stomach and intestines. In addition, in connection with the possibility of the formation of antibiotic resistance of *H. pylori*, it is necessary to develop a strategy to stop this process, as well as search for alternative treatment methods for cases when drug resistance still develops [16].

There is an opinion that in the future it is necessary to develop a vaccine for the prevention of *H. pylori* infection in countries with a large number of *H. pylori* carriers and with a proven connection between *H. pylori* infection and stomach cancer, as well as in families where a disease of the gastrointestinal tract associated with this infection has already been diagnosed.

The fight against infection caused by *H. pylori* is currently a global problem, and its solution will prevent the development of complications [17]. During the analysis of the available data on the problem of spread, pathogenesis, diagnosis and treatment of chronic gastritis and peptic ulcer disease, the relevance of studying this infection and the need to increase the effectiveness of anti-helicobacter therapy, namely, minimization of the inflammatory response of the mucous membranes of the stomach and duodenum in combination with the eradication of *H. pylori* infection.

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